

LATIN AND INTRODUCTION TO DECLENSIONS

Olimzoda Parvina

Assistant Teacher of the Department of Languages,
Samarkand State Medical University

Ahmed Bilal

The Student of International Faculty, Samarkand State Medical University

Abstract. Latin is a classical language known for its grammar and declensions. This comprehensive and guide the world of Latin declensions providing an in-depth understanding of the fundamentals of language. There are mainly 5 types of declensions in the Latin language which are further mentioned and explained separately in the article.

Key words: concepts, declension, Latin grammar, vocabulary, nouns, nominative, genitive

Introduction. Latin is referred to as the "language of the Romans" holds a special place in the history of language and remains a key foundation for many modern languages. A system of word endings that convey essential information about case number, and gender. In this article we will explore the five main Latin declensions, mentioning their rules, and patterns in the structure of this language.

First Declension. The first declension consists of feminine nouns. These nouns are often associated with objects or gender concepts such as feminine. In the first declension, the nominative singular ends in "a," and the genitive singular ends in "ae." It is important to know that these noun endings change as we move from the nominative, genitive singular and plural, singular and plural and ablative singular and plural. Gender plays an important role in Latin, impacting noun forms and agreement with other words in a sentence.

Second Declension. The second declension contains both masculine and neuter nouns, this offers a various range of grammar. Masculine nouns in the second declension sometimes denote male, while neuter gender nouns represent objects or concepts that lack gender. The nominative singular forms of masculine nouns often end in "us," while neuter nouns end in "-um." The genitive singular generally ends in "i." Knowing the difference

between masculine and neuter nouns within their adjectival statement is essential to the complexes of latin

The second declension encompasses both masculine and neuter nouns, offering a diverse range of vocabulary. Masculine nouns in the second declension often denote male beings, while neuter nouns typically represent objects or concepts that lack gender. The nominative singular forms of masculine nouns often end in "-us," while neuter nouns end in "-um." The genitive singular usually ends in "i." Understanding the distinction between masculine and neuter nouns within this declension is essential. Adjectives, which must agree in gender, number, and case with nouns, declension pattern of second-declension nouns, adding another layer of complexity Latin.

Third Declension. The third declension is difficult and challenging in Latin. Nouns in this declension can be masculine, feminine, or neuter. The nominative and genitive singular forms can be highly irregular, making memorization an important component of learning. Various examples showcase the diversity in endings within the third declension, underscoring the importance of recognizing and recalling these forms. For instance, "rex" (king) is a masculine third-declension noun with forms like "regis" (of the king) in the genitive. The third declension also introduces learnings to some common 3rd declension adjectives and pronouns which are essential for forming well structured sentences in Latin.

Fourth and Fifth Declensions. The fourth and fifth declensions are less common than the first three but hold their unique significance. The fourth declension mainly involves masculine nouns, which are characterized by nominative singular forms ending in "us" and genitive singular forms ending in "us" as well. The fourth declension shows the flexibility of Latin grammar. For example, "dominus" (master) is a fourth-declension masculine noun, with forms like "domini" (of the master) in the genitive. The fifth declension is typically connected with feminine nouns, and the nominative singular forms of these nouns often end in "es," while the genitive singular ends in "ei." Understanding the fifth declension is very important for those looking to explore Latin grammar, as it involves a specific set of words not frequently used in everyday language. For example, "res" (matter/thing) is a feminine fifth-declension noun, with forms like "rei" "of the matter" in the genitive.

The V declension includes feminine nouns, which in the genitive case have the ending -ei, for example, facies, ei f "face", surface, this noun is the only representative of the V

declension in anatomical and histological nomenclature. It should be noted that that the sound [e] in the ending -ei after the final sound of the stem i is long and therefore percussive (an exception to the rule of brevity vowels).

Summarizing the above, we note that the anatomical terms rarely consist of one word. Most often you have to deal with terms consisting of two, three or more words. The main word in the term is, of course, the noun. You should immediately remember that any term begins with words of a noun in the nominative case (singular or plural). As a rule, the main word has carry with you a definition (one or more) that can be expressed by adjectives (agreed definitions) or nouns in the genitive case (inconsistent definitions).

Construction noun + noun in genus item in anatomical and histological nomenclature occurs very often, and learn correctly construct a term with an inconsistent relationship means being able to form a variety of anatomical terms. The order of words in inconsistent phrases does not differ from the order of words in a similar construction of the Russian language: neck (noun in noun) + shoulder blades (noun in gender). In Latin these are: collum (Nom. Sg.) + scapulae (Gen. Sg.). Sometimes genitive the case of the noun is translated into Russian by the adjective: venae portal “portal vein” (vein of the gate). An inconsistent definition may include two nouns in genitive case: ligamentum tuberculi (definition of the word ligamentum), costae (definition of the word tuberculi) “ligament of the tubercle of the rib”.

Conclusion. As we talk about the conclusion, learning Latin declensions is a very important step in acquiring control in this language. The five declensions shows the structure and foundation of Latin language, it also convey meanings and sentences. understanding the gender, case and number of nouns and their adjective agreements is important for uncovering the beauty of Latin language. Regular practice and usage are key of mastering these declensions.

LITERATURE:

1. Karimovna, Y. S. (2022). The linguistic environment in the field of medical communications. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 2(2), 143-147.
2. Karimovna, Y. S. Social-cultural Characteristics of Uzbek and English Medical Speech. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 4(5), 294-298.
3. Karimovna, Y. S. Medicine and Education faculty Samarkand State Medical Institute.

4. Karimovna, Y. S., & Farxodovna, R. K. VISION. THE MAIN VISUAL IMPAIRMENT IN ADOLESCENTS. *Zbiór artykułów naukowych recenzowanych.*, 45.

5. Ученых, Е. С. 12 (69), 2019 LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES FOR MEDICAL INSTITUTIONS Nuritdinova Zulkhumor Shamsievna Head of Chair in Samarkand State Medical Institute. *Yorova Sayora Karimovna English teacher of Samarkand State Medical Institute*, 9, 26.

6. Karimovna, Y. S., Erkinovna, T. N., & Agwan, A. (2023). MODERN EDUCATION AND CULTURAL DEVELOPMENT NURTURING GLOBAL CITIZENS IN THE 21ST CENTURY. *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*, 9(11), 292-294.

7. Saydullaevna, N. N., & Karimovna, Y. S. COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING”, “ADVANTAGES OF THE TECHNIQUE WHAT/HOW/WHY OUTLINES IN DEVELOPING PRODUCTIVE SKILLS OF THE MEDICAL STUDENTS. In *Контактная информация организационного комитета конференции* (p. 135).

8. Saydullaevna, N. N., & Karimovna, Y. S. COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING”, “ADVANTAGES OF THE TECHNIQUE WHAT/HOW/WHY OUTLINES IN DEVELOPING PRODUCTIVE SKILLS OF THE MEDICAL STUDENTS. In *Контактная информация организационного комитета конференции* (p. 135).

9. Karimovna, Y. S. (2020). COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF A SPECIALIST. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol*, 8(4).

10. Karimovna, Y. S., & Sachdeva, L. (2023). DIFFERENT APPROACHES AND ISSUES OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE IN CONTEXT OF GLOBALIZATION. *TALIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 3(5), 226-229.

11. Ilhomjonovna, S. K., & Parvina, O. (2020). Structural-Morphological Characteristics of Binary Tautologisms. *International Journal on Orange Technologies*, 2(12), 23-28.

12. Shamsiyev, K., Olimzoda, P., Saidova, K., & Ibragimova, D. (2023, February). APPROACHES TO TEACHING ACADEMIC WRITING. In *Международная конференция академических наук* (Vol. 2, No. 2, pp. 31-34).

13. Saidova, K., Ibragimova, D., Olimzoda, P., & Shamsiyev, K. (2023). INFLUENCE OF USING GAMES ON ENGLISH LESSONS. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(4), 54-58.

14. Shodikulova, A. Z. (2021). Methodology For Using Computer Training Programs In English Lessons. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, 12(13), 3358-3367.

15. Olimzoda, P. (2022). Usage of video as audiovisual materials in foreign language classes. *Science and Education*, 3(11), 800-803.

16. Нормуродова, Н., Уралова, Ч., & Олимзода, П. (2021). The role of extracurricular activities in foreign language teaching. *Общество и инновации*, 2(5/S), 12-16.

17. Parvina, O. (2023). TYPES OF TEXTBOOKS AND THEIR EVALUATION. *Journal of new century innovations*, 22(4), 50-54.

18. Parvina, O. (2023). Theoretical and Methodological Foundations for the Formation of Communicative Competence of Medical Students. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education*, 1(3), 1-3.

19. Ibragimova, D. S., Saidova, K. I., & Olimzoda, P. THE EFFICACY OF PROFICIENT READING STRATEGIES IN ENHANCING READING COMPETENCIES.

20. Парвина, О. (2023). ОСНОВНАЯ РОЛЬ ДОПОЛНИТЕЛЬНЫХ ЗАНЯТИЙ В ОБУЧЕНИЕ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫК. *Research Focus*, 2(10), 69-74.

21. Ҳахуяевна, N. S. (2023). ANALYZING DIALECTS AND WRITTEN DOCUMENTS IN MIDDLE ENGLISH PERIOD. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(6), 458-463.

22. Nasimova, S. (2023). PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGE AS THE SECOND LANGUAGE. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(11), 203-207.

23. Саматова, Г. Н., & Насимова, С. (2016). Прагматический подход к преподаванию на английском языке. *Научный альманах*, (6-1), 605-607.

24. Yaxyayevna, N. S. (2023). FONOLOGIYA VA UNING TURLARI. " XXI ASRDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR, FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" nomli respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi, 1(12), 5-9.

25. Nasimova Sohiba Yaxyayevna, & Mohammad Aftab Alam. (2023). INTRODUCTION INTO ANATOMICAL HISTOLOGICAL TERMINOLOGY. NOUN, GRAMMAR CATEGORIES OF NOUNS. DETERMINATIONS OF GENDER, STEM, VOCABULARY FORMS. *Yangi O'zbekistonda Tabiiy Va Ijtimoiy-Gumanitar Fanlar Respublika Ilmiy Amaliy Konferensiyasi*, 1(7), 107–111. Retrieved from <https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/gumanitar/article/view/2974>

26. Nasimova Sohiba Yaxyayevna, & Taha Khalid. (2023). TOPIC PRESCRIPTION STRUCTURE OF PRESCRIPTION. *International Conference on Multidisciplinary Science*, 1(5), 210–214. Retrieved from <https://mjtjournal.com/index.php/icms/article/view/396>

27. Yakhyaevna, N. S. (2023). HISTORY OF ENGLISH WRITING DOCUMENTS IN THE MIDDLE AGES. *Research Focus*, 2(10), 41-45.

28. Yaxyayevna, N. S., & Alam, M. A. (2023). INTRODUCTION INTO ANATOMICAL HISTOLOGICAL TERMINOLOGY. NOUN, GRAMMAR CATEGORIES OF NOUNS. DETERMINATIONS OF GENDER, STEM, VOCABULARY FORMS. *Yangi O'zbekistonda Tabiiy va Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar respublika ilmiy amaliy konferensiyasi*, 1(7), 107-111.

29. Yaxyayevna, N. S., & Khalid, T. (2023, November). TOPIC PRESCRIPTION STRUCTURE OF PRESCRIPTION. In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 1, No. 5, pp. 210-214).

30. Fomina Mayde Anatolevna ,Shodikulova Aziza Zikirayevna. (2023). DEONTOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF WINGED SAYINGS IN MEDICINE. *Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 10(10), 124–125. Retrieved from <http://www.eijmr.org/index.php/eijmr/article/view/343>

31. Фомина, М. А., & Шамсиев, К. К. (2020). КРЫЛАТЫЕ ИЗРЕЧЕНИЯ. *Глобус*, (1 (47)), 100-101.

32. Фомина, М. А., Бабаева, Д. Х., & Бекнзарова, М. К. (2019). О СЛОВООБРАЗОВАНИИ В МЕДИЦИНСКОЙ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИИ. *Кронос: психология и педагогика*, (1 (18)), 20-21.

33. Фомина, М. А., & Бекназарова, М. К. (2021, January). МЕДИЦИНСКИЕ ТЕКСТЫ НА АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ. In *The 5th International scientific and practical conference "World science: problems, prospects and innovations"* (January 27-29, 2021) Perfect Publishing, Toronto, Canada. 2021. 1300 p. (p. 1158).

34. Фомина, М. А., & Тураев, А. Ю. (2020). ЛИМЕРИКИ КАК ПОЛЕЗНОЕ РАЗВЛЕЧЕНИЕ. In *ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ* (pp. 60-66).

35. Fomina, M. (2023). ADABIY ASARLARDAN KIRIB KELGAN SO 'Z BIRIKMALARINING TIBBIYOTDAGI DEONTOLOGIK MA'NOSI. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 3(10), 284-286.

36. Фомина, М. А. (2023). Роль приставок в медицинской терминологии. *Science and Education*, 4(2), 1696-1699.

37. Fomina, M. A. (2022). The English Language in Medical High School. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INCLUSIVE AND SUSTAINABLE EDUCATION*, 1(4), 170-171.

38. Normurodova, S. M., & Yorova, S. K. (2023). Nemis tili frazeologik birikmalari va tilning lug'at boyligi. *Science and Education*, 4(2), 1672-1675.

39. Sohiba, N., & Perkhan, A. (2023). THE ROLE OF LATIN TERMS IN MEDICINE. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429*, 12(10), 1-3.

40. Zafar, M., & Sohiba, N. (2023). KUNDALIK TURMUSHDA KENG QO'LLANILISHDA BO'LGAN SUYUQLIKLARNI IFODALOVCHI DORI SHAKLLARI HAQIDA CHET EL ILMIY NASHRLARIDAN OLINGAN FIKRLAR. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 2(5), 199-204.

41. Soxiba, N. (2023). SYNTACTICAL STRUCTURE OF BINARY TAUTOLOGISMS. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429*, 12(11), 53-56.

42. Mallaevna, N. S., & Khalid, A. (2023, November). TOPIC CHEMICAL TERMINOLOGY OF SALTS. In *International conference on multidisciplinary science* (Vol. 1, No. 5, pp. 226-229).

ISSN (E): 2181-4570 ResearchBib Impact Factor: 6,4 / 2023 SJIF(2023)-3,778 Volume-2, Issue-1

43. Zafar, M. Normurodova sohiba.(2023). Kundalik turmushda keng qo'llanilishda bo'lgan suyuqliklarni ifodalovchi dori shakllari haqida chet el ilmiy nashrlaridan olingan fikrlar. *Involta scientific journal*, 2 (5), 199–204.

44. Mallaevna, N. S. (2023). THE MAIN INDICATORS OF THE COMMUNICATION CULTURE OF A MEDICAL WORKER. *JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH*, 6(7), 85-88.

45. Mallaevna, N. S., & Fatima, M. (2023). PATHOLOGICAL CONDITIONS AND PROCESSES, DIFFERENT PHYSICAL PROPERTIES QUALITIES AND OTHER SIGNS. *Yangi O'zbekistonda Tabiiy va Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar respublika ilmiy amaliy konferensiyasi*, 1(7), 91-95.

46. Нормуродова, С. М. (2022). Тиббий атамаларни шакллантириш усуллари. *Science and Education*, 3(12), 1176-1181.

